

Cosmology of Uniform Empty Space

Космология Равномерного Пустого Пространства

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Abstract

The metric is obtained of isotropic and uniform empty space. The only parameter of this metric has dimensionality of the Hubble constant. The Einstein tensor allows computing the energy-momentum tensor of the empty space. Density of the space turned to be equal to the critical density in the Friedmann's theory. Also from the same metric, it follows that the exponential law of a red shift change as a function of time is asymptotically close to the Hubble's law.

Keywords: Metric of Universe, Red shift, Dark energy, Accelerated expansion, Incurvature of space, Density of Universe, Negative pressure.

Абстрактные

Получена метрика изотропного и равномерного пустого пространства. Единственный параметр этой метрики имеет размерность константы Хаббла. Тензор Эйнштейна позволяет вычислить тензор энергии-импульса пустого пространства. Плотность пространства оказалась равной критической плотности в теории Фридмана. Из той же метрики следует, что экспоненциальный закон изменения красного смещения как функция времени асимптотически близок к закону Хаббла.

Ключевые слова: Метрика Вселенной, Красное смещение, Темная энергия, Ускоренное расширение, Невидимость пространства, Плотность Вселенной, Отрицательное давление.

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1. Introduction

The metric is obtained of isotropic and uniform empty space. The only parameter of this metric has dimensionality of the Hubble constant. The Einstein tensor allows computing the energy-momentum tensor of the empty space. Density of the space turned to be equal to the critical density in the Freedman's theory. Also from the same metric, it follows that the exponential law of a red shift change as a function of time is asymptotically close to the Hubble's law. [1]

A. Einstein and A. A. Freedman considered the Universe to be filled by matter. The paper [2] laid the foundations of the concept of the non-stationary Universe. The discovery of the cosmological red shift and A. Einstein's support [3] determined the cosmology development for many years to come.

Here we shall try and describe a background space of the Universe without a matter relying only on the relativity principle and the Riemannian geometry.

1. Development

1.1. Light velocity constancy

The light velocity constancy is the necessary condition of the relativity principle. Einstein and Fokker [4] noticed that a reference system with a constant local light velocity is described by the metric of the following kind:

$$ds^2 = v^2(dx_0^2 - dx_1^2 - dx_2^2 - dx_3^2), \quad (1)$$

where v is a function of coordinates². The constancy of the velocity follows from the fact that the equation $ds^2 = 0$ describes the wave front having the fixed local velocity c .

The space with the metric (1) can be classified as conformally Galilean one [5].

Let us consider a space with uniform derivatives of coordinates on time of second order. In the frame of reference, in which points have zero velocity,

components of four-acceleration of a point are equal to

$$\frac{d^2x^i}{dt^2} = -c^2\Gamma_{00}^i = c^2k_i.$$

Let us require that the metric (1) is uniform on acceleration, i.e. the acceleration value c^2k_i does not depend on coordinates. This condition is met by the metric³

$$ds^2 = \exp(2k_ix_i)(dx_0^2 - dx_1^2 - dx_2^2 - dx_3^2).$$

In a case that $k_i = 0$, this is the metric of the Minkowski space (if at least one of k_i is equal to zero). But in the case that only $k_0 = 0$, this is the metric of a uniformly accelerated system [7]. The assumption that the entire universe has non-zero acceleration in one direction is extremely incredible. The only possible left version is the metric with the non-zero component of the vector k_0 , which looks like as follows:

$$ds^2 = \exp(2k_0x_0)(dx_0^2 - dx_1^2 - dx_2^2 - dx_3^2). \quad (2)$$

It is significant that the Einstein tensor of this metric is not equal to zero. The metric (2) has the strictly negative scalar curvature $R = -6k_0^2 \exp(-2k_0x_0)$ regardless of a position of the origin of coordinates.

It is well known that the covariant divergence of Einstein tensor is equal to zero. This allows associating it with the energy-momentum tensor. The constant of proportionality between these values is known from their asymptotical behavior in the Newtonian approximation⁴. These speculations allow computing the energy-momentum tensor as follows:

² From this result, the authors came to the generally covariant Nordstrom's equation. However the Nordstrom's scalar theory failed in the competition with the general relativity theory.

³ This metric can be considered to be a generalization of the exact result obtained by Einstein as long ago as in 1907 [6] for a uniform field of accelerations $d\tau = \exp(ax/c^2)dt$.

⁴ Einstein's converse equation.

$$\frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \left(R_{ik} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ik} R \right) = \begin{pmatrix} 3p & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -p \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where $p = \frac{c^2 H_0^2}{8\pi G}$.

So indeed, the metric (2) describes the uniform space-time having the constant density and the negative pressure at any point of the space.

The space density of the uniform metric $\rho = 3p/c^2$ coincides surprisingly with the Freedman's critical density [8]

$$\rho_{cr} = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}$$

For a fixed in space observer, the own time of a light source is connected with the observer's time on a distance x_0 by the ratio:

$$d\tau = \exp(k_0 x_0) dt.$$

In a case that $T = x_0/c$ is time of signal delay, after imposing $ck_0 = H_0$, we shall obtain the red shift close to the Hubble's law

$$z = \exp(H_0 T) - 1 \approx H_0 T. \quad (4)$$

However with a distance growth to the source, the red shift grows faster than the Hubble's law.

1.2. Energy-momentum tensor

Quite expected is the fact that the energy-momentum tensor (3) of a uniform field is constant all around the space. From this result, it follows that *at any instant of time*, the observer *being situated in any point* will be in the same conditions and see the same red shift (4). This red shift is equivalent to the acceleratedly expanding Universe (4). We see that the Hubble's law extrapolation to the past does not necessarily retract the Universe into a point (see Figure 1).

2. Conclusion

Let us pay attention that **the result is obtained without use of the Freedman's equation or any**

hypotheses using the lambda-member. It is possible that the uniform space metric (2) can serve as a background for cosmological models construction.

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Figure 1. Signal delay is a window into a past of the universe with a slow time run. **Source:** [9]

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